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Teachers' Views and Attitudes on the Organization and Implementation of the Social and Emotional Intelligence Education Program

Dr. Vasiliki Brinia¹, Aikaterini Athanasiou²

¹ Teacher Education Program, Athens University of Economics and Business, vbrinia@aueb.gr

² Hellenic Open University, Katerina_a8anasiou@hotmail.com

Abstract

The present study examines teachers' views in the 30th Region of Primary Education of Attica, Greece in relation to the organization and implementation of the Social and Emotional Intelligence Education Program. The quantitative method was applied in the present investigation, and the questionnaire shared contained questions from three different pillars. Findings, deriving from teachers' and head teachers' views, show that there are differences between women and men as well as between head teachers and teachers, in terms of emotions expressed in teachers' work, desire to become ideal teachers, satisfaction by the profession, desire to remain in same profession and familiarity with this Program. Also, there are differences in terms of the recognition they feel they receive and of the feeling that the implementation of the Program improves their working environment. Overall, women understand better the emotions of others, use better communication strategies for students and parents, consider that the Program improves the school environment, develops students' and teachers' relationships, and the training for its implementation is crucial. Similar differences are also observed in the comparison between teachers and head teachers. The present study is one of the few of this kind that exists and reflects the teachers' views and attitudes who have implemented such Programs in a particular educational district.

Key Words: Emotional Intelligence, EQ, Self-Esteem, Emotional Strategy, Emotional Fulfillment, Social and Emotional Intelligence Education Program

1. Introduction

This paper attempts to examine teachers' emotional intelligence as well as their views on the implementation of the Social and Emotional Intelligence Education Program. Indeed, within the spur of change and new curricula, the teacher is called upon to play the role of facilitator, counselor, educator (Duskas, 2005). Teachers, to cope with their difficult work, they must be emotionally intelligent and empathic to recognize their emotions, manipulate them (Neophytou, 2013), and be able to manage students and parents properly. In the present study, teachers' emotional intelligence is examined through the emotional self-esteem, the emotional strategies and the emotional satisfaction they have in their profession, their views on the Social and Emotional Intelligence Program and the value of the training for its implementation.

Purpose and Objectives of the Study

The purpose of this proposal is to explore teachers' and head teachers' views of the 30th Primary Education Region of Attica, Greece that has implemented the Social and Emotional Intelligence Program, with respect to how they implemented it and the benefits to their students.

The aims of the present study are to show the importance of the Social and Emotional Intelligence Education Program in the educational process and, above all, to highlight the teachers' and the head teachers' role in the implementation of these programs.

The purpose leads to the following research questions:

1. What is the level of the emotional and social intelligence of the research teachers and does this affect their views-experience from the Program implemented in their school unit?
2. What are the teachers' views involved in the implementation of the Social and Emotional Intelligence Program, about its value and its usefulness in school in general?
3. How were teachers educated and trained to implement this Program?

2. Literature Review

2.1. The Concept of Emotional Intelligence

Intelligence is a multidimensional feature that consists of a combination of skills that complement each other and help individuals to understand, manage and address issues that are presented to them.

Salovey, Mayer and Caruso gave the official definition of emotional intelligence by defining it as the ability of individuals to recognize their own first emotions and then to distinguish emotions and use them in a way that guides their thoughts and actions and to solve the problems presented to them (Mayer, Salovey & Caruso, 2000).

According to Bradberry & Greaves (2006), individuals have three complementary abilities that help them determine their thoughts and behavior:

- the Intelligence Index,
- Emotional Intelligence,
- the personality.

It should not be overlooked that individuals' emotional intelligence is not an inherent characteristic of the personality, but it indicates the level of individuals' emotional competence to interact with themselves and other people in their environment. What is emphasized is that emotional intelligence as a concept is different from personality (Law et al., 2004), but it is referred to as the individuals' competence to be able to personally handle the emotions of other people around them (Naqvi et al., 2016). However,

2.2. Social Intelligence

In the early studies, psychologists argued that cognitive abilities are those that help the individuals solve the problems they are facing. Thorndike, however, in 1920, differentiated and used the term Social Intelligence as a concept introducing emotional intelligence, trying to define the individuals' ability to perceive themselves, recognize their motives and behavior, and interact with other people (Landy, 2005).

2.3. Multiple Intelligence

Gardner, studying the concept of intelligence, analyzed it in eight genres, namely linguistic, mathematical, logical, visual, musical, kinesthetic, interpersonal and intrapersonal. The two

forms of intelligence, however, that contribute to personal and professional success are Intrapersonal and Interpersonal Intelligence, which are the basis for the development of Emotional Intelligence (Gardner, 1983). More specifically, intrapersonal intelligence refers to the ability of individuals to recognize and understand their own moods, desires, motives, and intentions, and interpersonal intelligence is the ability of an individual to recognize and understand the moods and desires of other people.

2.4. Emotional Intelligence according to Bar-On

Bar-On, in the mid-1980s, defines emotional intelligence as a set of skills and abilities that help individuals successfully meet the challenges of their social environment (Platsidou, 2004) and considers it to be inextricably linked with social skills and skills of the individual. He introduced E.Q. (Emotional Quotient) and developed the EQ-i (Emotional Quotient Inventory) as a tool for measuring social and emotional functions associated with psychological development (Bar-On & Parker, 2000), which is structured into five components.

2.5. The mixed model

Goleman emphasizes that emotional intelligence includes a range of social and communication skills and relates to how emotion management, self-knowledge, self-management, social awareness, and social skills are effective factors for the development of the person (Boyatzis, Goleman, & Rhee, 2000) and the formation of an effective behavior (Neophytou & Koutselini, 2006).

2.6. Teachers' emotional intelligence

Teaching is not only the ability of the educator to convey knowledge, but it is also an interactive and two-way relationship. That is why emotions play an essential role in teaching, enhancing the teachers' personal and professional identity. (Uitto, Jokikokko, & Estola, 2015).

Teaching, then, is an interaction, a communication of individuals (Uitto, Jokikokko, & Estola, 2015). Teachers, in order to teach, must firstly manage their students appropriately to facilitate their psychological development (Naqvi et al., 2016) to create relationships of security and trust (Buyse et al., 2008), reducing in this way the risk of aggressive behaviors (Dominguez et al., 2011). Also, they must have developed a proper communication with their students' parents, head teacher, and colleagues, and they should have a positive attitude towards life. Consequently, in order to become effective, they should consider how they teach beyond intellectual competence, professional skills and academic qualifications (Naqvi et al., 2016).

Based on the literature review, research on teachers' emotions was initially scarce and mainly centered on the field of cognition, behavior, skills, and performance (Uitto, Jokikokko, & Estola, 2015), thinking, research of "negative" emotions or disorders (Sutton, & Wheatley, 2003). The results of these surveys show that the way teachers manage their emotions creates a positive environment in the classroom, while their emotional weaknesses affect students and make their interactions more difficult (Denham, Bassett, & Zinsser, 2012) and this may lead to inappropriate approaches and impede student performance (Naqvi, et al., 2016). Teachers, who have a high degree of emotional intelligence, and use it as a skill, use it in the process of education (Yin, Lee & Zhang, 2013) to get better performance and to teach in more effective ways (Ghanizadeh & Moafian, 2010). This finding is also highlighted by Kremenitzer (2005),

who links the teacher's emotional intelligence with effective teaching. In addition, they work better with their colleagues, even those with lower emotional intelligence (Nizielski et al., 2012).

In the field of leadership, high emotional intelligence pushes head teachers to be more effective and to better support teachers (Brackett, et al., 2010). In addition, it encourages them to perceive personal emotions and to handle negative ones in a spirit of understanding, to approach others around them, to prove themselves as emotionally intelligent leaders who can guide and direct them (Prati et al., 2003). Another area of emotional intelligence contributes to communication. Survey results show that emotional intelligence develops one of the key features of teacher profile, their communication skills (Gursimek et al., 2008). That is why the teacher must be emotionally balanced.

Emotional intelligence, therefore, has a central place among teachers in schools, colleges and universities (Jennings & Greenberg, 2009). This is why many researchers emphasize that the selection criteria in education for both head teachers and teachers should include emotional competencies and interpersonal relationships in order to achieve better work performance (Iordanoglou, 2007; Brinia & Perakaki, 2018) and even more be a good predictor of performance (Corcoran et al., 2013).

2.7. Students' Emotional Intelligence

Modern education focuses on how to help children acquire both cognitive and emotional skills that will be useful to them in their lives. Goleman notes that one of the factors that help the adult to succeed in life is intrapersonal intelligence, which refers to abilities arising from high emotional intelligence, communication techniques, interpersonal relationships, time management (Low & Nelson, 2005) and knowledge obtained from school years with appropriate education (Elias, 2003).

More specifically, teachers, who act as mentors, control and coordinate the course, observe students' behavior, help and give directions to their students so that they can emotionally support them and lead them to recognize their emotions, improve their interpersonal relationships (Denham et al., 2010; Brinia & Psoni, 2018), the development of communication between them (Zins et al., 2004). They take initiatives when necessary, use a variety of strategies and methods, ensure that a safe classroom is created and improve learning through positive encouragement and feedback (Haskett, 2003) (López-González & Oriol, 2016). Besides, according to Dewey, communication, emotion, and learning are intertwined in the classroom (Titsworth et al., 2010), and by creating an appropriate pedagogical atmosphere (Duskas, 2005), students communicate and express themselves more easily, form relationships of trust and emotional interaction.

2.8. Social and Emotional Intelligence Programs at School

At school, problems are mainly those that affect the learning process, such as dyslexia. At the same time, however, there is an increase in the problems related to the psychological, emotional and social situation of children. Therefore, the implementation of programs for the Social and Emotional Intelligence of students is very widespread, because it helps their overall success (Zins et al., 2004).

Programs for Social and Emotional Intelligence are divided into three categories, including primary, secondary and tertiary prevention (Chatzihristou, 2004). More specifically, primary

prevention programs target large groups of the student population, they are distinguished in programs of Social and Emotional Intelligence and solving interpersonal problems (Chatzihristou, 2004) and can be implemented in the school environment by well-educated teachers. Zins (2007), notes that it is important within the school environment to enhance social-emotional development because school is a social part and learning is a social process. Secondary prevention programs are implemented by school psychologists and, finally, tertiary prevention programs are individual programs that are implemented for students with diagnosed disorders (Chatzichristou 2004).

Chryssi Chatzihristou, focusing on the role of the school for the positive development and mental well-being of the students, as head of the Center for Research and Applications of School Psychology by the University of Athens (CRASPUA), implemented the Program of Social and Emotional Intelligence Education in Primary Schools in Greece and Cyprus. This is an optional Primary Prevention Program for developing social and emotional skills.

3. Methodology

In order to investigate the issue, the quantitative method was considered to be the most appropriate, in order to produce data from which to draw general conclusions in a quick way (Kyriazis, 2009). In this study, a representative sample was used as a sample which yielded valid results and allowed the researcher to generalize the results (Korres, 2007). More generally, sampling, as a method of quantitative research, helps to draw out objective conclusions, since the researcher and the participants are at a certain distance and the result is difficult to affect (Creswell, 2011).

The 30th Athens Primary Education Region includes 14 schools in which 136 Primary Education teachers work. Of these, 20 implemented the Social and Emotional Intelligence Education Program (27,2%) and participated in the survey. Also, 10 of the 14 school principals who implemented the Program took part in the survey, and this was because at the end of the school year, because of head teachers' evaluations, some of them retired.

Initially, school units in the 30th Region received a written invitation from their own School Advisor to inform 5th and 6th grade teachers about the implementation of the Social and Emotional Intelligence Program by Chrissi Chatzihristou. Those who wished could take part in its specialized training and implementation in their classes during the Flexible Zone hours.

For the survey, a questionnaire consisting of 30 questions was used as a tool, using the 5-point Likert-scale as well as closed type questions, so that the time of completion by the participants was not inhibitory.

In the questionnaire, the first five questions relate to personal data. The following questions are divided into three pillars.

The first pillar: "Teachers' Emotional Intelligence and Professional Development" includes nineteen questions divided into three sections:

- Emotional self-esteem and teachers (questions 6-13)
- The emotional strategy at work (questions 14-20)
- The teacher's emotional satisfaction with the profession (questions 21-24)

The second pillar: "The Benefits of the Social and Emotional Intelligence Program for Students and Improving the School Environment" includes three questions (questions 25-27).

The third pillar: "Teachers' Training and Vocational Training for the Implementation of the Program" includes three questions (28-30), and the 5-point Likert scale is used.

The analysis of the data was done with the statistical program SPSS Statistics 24, a handy and widespread program used in quantitative sample survey methods (Creswell, 2011). The analysis included first, descriptive statistical measures and then comparisons with the χ^2 test (comparison of percentages) and the t-test of independent samples (average comparison).

4. Findings

1st pillar

The first pillar of the questionnaire refers to teachers' emotional intelligence and professional development and is divided into three sub-sections:

A. The first subsection addresses the teachers' emotional self-esteem.

The t-test showed that teachers statistically significantly higher:

- a. recognize their feelings (4.16 ± 0.59) with respect to the head teachers (3.76 ± 0.53), $t(78) = 2.78$, $p = 0.00$,
- b. control their feelings (4.13 ± 0.47) with respect to the head teachers (3.81 ± 0.51), $t(78) = 2.66$, $p = 0.00$,
- c. understand their emotions (4.27 ± 0.52) with respect to the head teachers (3.52 ± 0.51), $t(78) = 5.68$, $p = 0.00$.

B. The second subsection addresses the emotional strategy at work.

The t-test showed that men statistically significantly lower:

- a. manage students and parents (4.04 ± 0.21) than women (4.23 ± 0.42), $t(78) = -1.99$, $p = 0.05$,
- b. show false emotions to students and parents (1.74 ± 1.09) than women (2.54 ± 1.13), $t(78) = -2.90$, $p = 0.00$,
- c. pretend they have emotions in the workplace (1.69 ± 1.97) compared to women (2.73 ± 1.02), $t(78) = -4.16$, $p = 0.00$,
- d. work hard to show the emotions they must to students and parents (1.95 ± 1.15) than women (3.42 ± 0.73), $t(78) = -6.83$, $p = 0.00$,
- e. show true emotions to students and parents (3.00 ± 0.60) compared to women (3.73 ± 1.09), $t(78) = -3.04$, $p = 0.00$,
- f. show natural and spontaneous emotions to students (3.39 ± 0.84) compared to women (4.19 ± 0.76), $t(78) = -4.12$, $p = 0.00$,
- g. show natural and spontaneous emotions to parents (2.40 ± 0.84) compared to women (3.42 ± 0.99), $t(78) = -4.29$, $p = 0.00$.

The t-test also showed that the teachers statistically significantly higher:

- a. manage teachers and parents properly (4.24 ± 0.43) with respect to the head teachers (4.00 ± 0.00), $t(78) = 2.52$, $p = 0.01$.
- b. pretend to have emotion when in the workplace (2.76 ± 1.00) with respect to the head teachers (1.52 ± 0.87), $t(78) = 5.00$, $p = 0.00$,
- c. work to show the emotions they must to students and parents (3.25 ± 0.84) with respect to the head teachers (2.28 ± 1.38), $t(78) = 3.76$, $p = 0.00$.

C. The third subsection addresses the emotional satisfaction of the teacher with the profession.

The t-test showed that women statistically significantly higher:

- a. aspire to be ideal teachers (4.08 ± 0.74) with respect to men (2.65 ± 1.49), $t(78) = -5.75$, $p = 0.00$,
- b. are satisfied with the profession (4.09 ± 0.66) with respect to men (3.43 ± 0.73), $t(78) = -3.88$, $p = 0.00$,
- c. believe that being a teacher has a lot to offer them (4.58 ± 0.56) with respect to men (3.78 ± 0.73), $t(78) = -5.22$, $p = 0.00$,
- d) would again choose the same profession (4.19 ± 1.06) with respect to men (2.17 ± 1.40), $t(78) = -7.00$, $p = 0.00$.

The t-test also showed that the teachers statistically significantly higher:

- a. aspire to be ideal teachers (3.98 ± 0.75) with respect to the head teachers (2.80 ± 1.72), $t(78) = 4.24$, $p = 0.00$,
- b. declare satisfied with the profession (4.00 ± 0.67) with respect to the head teachers (3.61 ± 0.86), $t(78) = -2.06$, $p = 0.04$,
- c. believe that this profession has a lot of important things to offer them (4.71 ± 1.13) with respect to the head teachers (2.47 ± 1.75), $t(78) = 3.57$, $p = 0.00$,
- d. would again choose the same profession (4.19 ± 1.06) with respect to the head teachers (2.17 ± 1.40), $t(78) = 4.59$, $p = 0.00$.

2nd Pillar

The second pillar relates to the benefits of the Social and Emotional Intelligence Program to students and the improvement of the school environment.

The t-test showed the women, statistically significantly higher, to consider that this Program:

- a. improves the working environment (4.47 ± 0.50) with respect to men (4.00 ± 0.00), $t(78) = -4.50$, $p = 0.00$,
- b. improves student and teacher relationships (4.51 ± 0.50) with respect to men (4.09 ± 0.29), $t(78) = -3.76$, $p = 0.00$.

The t-test also showed the teachers, statistically significantly higher, to consider that this Program:

- a. improves the working environment (4.41 ± 0.50) with respect to the head teachers (4.00 ± 0.00), $t(78) = 2.23$, $p = 0.03$,
- b. improves the students' relations with teachers (4.53 ± 0.50) with respect to the head teachers (4.00 ± 0.00), $t(78) = 4.76$, $p = 0.00$.

3rd pillar

The third pillar relates to the teachers' training and vocational training for the implementation of the Program.

The t-test showed that women were, statistically significantly more familiar with the Program (3.18 ± 1.15) than men (1.95 ± 1.02). $T(78) = -4.42$, $p = 0.00$.

The t-test also showed (Table 43) that the teachers were statistically significantly more familiar with the Program (3.14 ± 1.10) than the head teachers (1.95 ± 1.20). $T(78) = 4.11$, $p = 0.00$.

5. Discussion of the Results

On the basis of the findings of the survey conducted, we will examine the questions raised. Initially, in the survey, two groups were included in the experimental group, which consisted of people who had implemented the Social and Emotional Intelligence Program in the classroom and the control group who had not implemented the specific Program. Of the participating teachers in both groups, men were less than women, and their ages ranged from 25 to 46+ years. Also, most teachers had a degree from Pedagogy Academy, had a degree of the same level or a postgraduate degree. Still, they were mostly teachers, and their teaching experience was for the experimental group from 16 to 30 years and for the control group from 21 to 30 years.

Subsequently, the research questions were divided into three pillars:

Teachers' Emotional Intelligence

The first research question referred to the teachers' level of emotional and social intelligence and was studied in the first pillar, which was divided into three sub-sections: emotional self-esteem, emotional strategy at work and emotional satisfaction from the profession. The teachers who participated in the research presented high scores in all three pillars of Emotional Intelligence that were examined, confirming the results of previous research (Platsidou, 2010, Chan, 2006) on the contribution of Emotional Intelligence to personality formation, motivation, professional development and in extension to the creation of a positive psychological environment within the classroom (Matsangouras & Makri-Botsari, 2003, Brinia & Psoni, 2016).

In more detail, the emotional self-esteem in the present study was quite high in both groups (M. = 30.96, S.D. = 1.71 for the experimental group and M. = 31.18, S.D. = 1,87 for the control group), with teachers having responded by "enough" to "very much" or "very much" and scored relatively high scores (929.00 in the experimental group and 1559.00 in the control team).

However, Cronbach's α -index was 0.34, indicating low reliability, contrary to the study by Hong-biao Yin, John Chi Kin Lee, Zhong-hua Zhang, Yu-le Jin (2013) which is 0,67-0,84 for the four subgroups in which the pillar questions are divided. This may be due to the fact that the sample of the present survey was small, while the sample in the research by Yin et al. (2013) is quite large (1281 teachers from elementary schools and high schools).

Then, by comparing the groups with each other in relation to emotional self-esteem, significant statistical differences were observed. The subjects in the experimental group had lower recognition of their emotions (3.87 ± 0.63 , $t(78) = -2.31$, $p = 0.02$). Statistical differences were also observed in gender comparisons with emotional self-esteem where women had a better understanding of their emotions (4.22 ± 0.50 , $t(78) = -3.81$, $p = 0.00$). However, as far as gender is concerned, the results of researches made, vary. Other studies, i.e. show that women have a better recognition of their emotions (Ciarrochi et.al., 2001, Nikolaou & Tsaousis, 2002), higher control of emotions (Petrides & Furnham, 2000) and are more sensitive to understanding others' emotions (Ciarrochi et al., 2000), while in other studies there are no significant differences (Dawda & Hart, 2000, Platsidou, 2010). Finally, statistical differences were also observed in the comparison of the position with respect to emotional self-esteem. Teachers appeared to better recognize their emotions (4.16 ± 0.59 , $t(78) = 2.78$, $p = 0.00$), better control (4.13 ± 0.47 , $t(78) = 2.66$, $p = 0.00$) and better understand the emotions of others around them (4.27 ± 0.52 $t(78) = 5.68$, $p = 0.00$).

More generally, emotional self-esteem shapes self-awareness and helps develop interpersonal relationships.

The second sub-section examined was the emotional strategy at work. From the survey data, the emotional strategy at work was high for both groups (M. = 21.33, S.D. = 4.36 for the experimental and M. = 23.26; S.D. = 5.25 for the control group). The value of Cronbach's α was 0.84, which is highly credible, just like the research by Yin et al. (2013) where the Cronbach's α is 0.74, 0.79 and 0.85 respectively for the three subgroups separated by pillar questions. More specifically, the teachers, both of which score a high score (experimental group 640.00 and control group 1163.00), stated that they use appropriate strategies in their work. Indeed, as Brouzos (2004) says, teachers with the strategies they apply in each case try to penetrate the student's inner world in order to understand the emotions better, the experiences he experiences and his problems.

Then, in the comparison of the groups with the emotional strategy at work, statistical differences of the groups (χ^2 , $p = 0.02 < 0.05$) were observed and even comparison with the t-test revealed that the subjects in the experimental group showed less false emotions to students and parents (1.96 ± 1.07 , $t(78) = -2.08$, $p = 0.04$) and were less likely to pretend to have emotions in their workplace (1.97 ± 1.00 , $t(78) = -3.08$, $p = 0.00$).

Also in the same sub-section, the teachers' communication with students and parents was pointed out. Teachers stated that they manage the students in an appropriate way. It is true that the teacher's communication with students influences the didactic act (Hargreaves, 2001) and at the same time, students perform better at the learning level and do not create problems in the classroom (Chatzidimou, 2000), when they love and like their teacher. In addition, in communicating with parents, the results showed that teachers properly manage the parents and show them genuine emotions. In the emotions they themselves had in the workplace, a high percentage replied that they were pretending to have emotions (36.70% in the experimental group and 48% in the control group), while a statistically significant difference in the groups was observed (χ^2 , $p = 0.02 < 0.05$). It is a fact that emotional relationships play an important role in the workplace (Uitto, Jokikokko & Estola, 2015) and depend on the emotional and social abilities of the person who, along with the competition (Cherniss, 2000) is led to show another side of himself trying to improve and succeed both personally and professionally (Karatzia-Stavlioti, 2002).

In the comparison of the genders, women appeared to manage better students and parents (4.23 ± 0.42 , $t(78) = -1.99$, $p = 0.05$), to show more false emotions to students and parents (2.54 ± 1.13 , $t(78) = -2.90$, $p = 0.00$), to pretend more to have emotions (2.73 ± 1.02 , $t(78) = -4.16$, $p = 0.00$), to show emotions they have to show (3.42 ± 0.73 , $t(78) = -6.83$, $p = 0.000$), to have more genuine emotions towards students and parents (3.73 ± 1.09 , $t(78) = -3.04$, $p = 0.00$), natural and spontaneous emotions towards students (4.19 ± 0.76 , $t(78) = -4.12$, $p = 0.00$), natural and spontaneous emotions towards parents (3.42 ± 0.99 , $t(78) = -4.29$, $p = 0.00$). The fact that women manage better than men, the emotions of others is referred to in Platsidou's research (2010). Also, the fact that women show more genuine, natural and spontaneous emotions towards the students is due to the fact that they have maternal emotions towards them (Reay, 2001). Regarding the comparison of the position, the teachers responded that they better manage students and parents (4.24 ± 0.43), $t(78) = 2.52$, $p = 0.01$, fake emotions in the workplace (2.76 ± 1.00), $t(78) = 5.00$, $p = 0.000$, but they also try hard to show the appropriate emotions each time (3.25 ± 0.84 , $t(78) = 3.76$, $p = 0.00$).

In conclusion, the teacher, with his emotional strategies, shapes the classroom learning environment and the way of communicating with his colleagues, students, and parents.

In the third sub-section, the teachers' satisfaction by their profession was high for both groups (M. = 14.96, S.D. = 3.79 in the experimental group and M. = 15.88, S.D. = 3.70 in the control group). Cronbach's α index was 0.88, showing high reliability with the same value being noted in Yin et al. (2013), which is 0.88. Thus, respondents, with a high score (experimental 449.00 and control group 794.00), said from "enough" to "very much" that they want to become ideal teachers, are satisfied with the profession that offers them important things, while from "no" to "very much," they said they would choose the same profession again. However, there were significant differences in the percentages of the groups, namely that they want to become ideal teachers (χ^2 , $p = 0.01 < 0.05$), are satisfied with the profession (χ^2 , $p = 0.04 < 0.05$) and would again choose the same profession (χ^2 , $p = 0.00 < 0.05$).

In general, the teachers' satisfaction from the profession appears in other surveys (Koustelios et al., 2006; Dinham & Scott, 2000; Reilly, Dhingra, Boduszek, 2013; Zembylas & Papanastasiou, 2006) and is very important for their professional development and performance.

In this sub-section, however, there were significant statistical differences between the genders. Women stated that they are more likely to become ideal teachers (4.08 ± 0.74 , $t(78) = -5.75$, $p = 0.00$), are satisfied with the profession (4.09 ± 0.66 , $t(78) = -3.88$, $p = 0.00$), which gives them important things (4.58 ± 0.56 , $t(78) = -5.22$, $p = 0.00$) and if they changed careers it would again be the same (4.19 ± 1.06 , $t(78) = -7.00$, $p = 0.00$). These differences between the genders may be due to the fact that the profession of a teacher is considered to be mainly female because it provides free time to the women which assists them in their duties as mothers (Papastylianou, Kaila, Polychronopoulos, 2009). Of course, the reasons why it is mostly chosen by women are not mentioned in this research, a parameter that could be considered in future research. Statistically significant differences were also observed in comparison with the place where teachers stated that they wanted to become ideal teachers (3.98 ± 0.75 , $t(78) = 4.24$, $p = 0.00$), are satisfied with the profession (4.00 ± 0.67 , $t(78) = -2.06$, $p = 0.042$) which gives them important things (4.01 ± 1.13 , $t(78) = 3.57$, $p = 0.00$) and would again choose the same (4.19 ± 1.06 , $t(78) = 4.59$, $p = 0.00$).

Teachers' views on the value and usefulness of the Social and Emotional Intelligence Education Program at school.

The second research question was analyzed in the second pillar. The results of the study revealed the benefits of the Program in the school (M. = 12.63, S.D. = 0.76 in the experimental group and control group M. = 13.18, S.D. = 1.08). More specifically, the answers show that the Program improves the working environment ("very" 80% + 20%, "very much" 58% + 42%), creates a positive attitude towards the school ("very" 83.3% + 70%, "Very much" 16.7% + 30%) and improves the students' relationship with teachers ("very" 73.3% + 54%, "very much" 26.7% + 46%). Accordingly, the Hallam (2009) survey shows that the Program improves the working environment (52% "very", 7% "very much"), creates a positive attitude towards school (53% "very" and 23% "very much") and improves the students' relationship with teachers (58% "very" and 7% "very much"). It is true that the implementation of the specific Program helps the school environment in general.

Then, in the comparison of the groups, the people in the experimental group considered that the specific Program did not greatly improve the working environment (4.20 ± 0.40 , $t(78) = -2.04$, $p = 0.04$). In contrast, in the gender comparison in the Program, female teachers

responded that its application improves not only the working environment (4.47 ± 0.50 , $t(78) = -4.50$, $p = 0.00$) but and student-teacher relationships (4.51 ± 0.50 , $t(78) = -3.76$, $p = 0.00$). The same was found in the comparison of the position in the program. That is why, the teachers responded that the Program helps to improve the working environment (4.41 ± 0.50 , $t(78) = 2.23$, $p = 0.03$) and the development of relations between students and teachers ($4, 53 \pm 0.50$, $t(78) = 4.76$, $p = 0.00$).

Teachers' Training and Vocational Training for the implementation of the Program

The third research question was analyzed in the third pillar of the survey. The results highlighted, with a high score (experimental 291.00 and control group 465.00), how useful the teachers' training and vocational training are for the implementation of the Program (M. = 9.70, S.D. = 1.70 in the test group and M. = 9.30, S.D. = 1.77 in the control group). In more detail, the survey showed that teachers were trained in the Program ("quite" 33.3% + 54% to "very much" 6.7% + 24%), , ("little" 0.0% + 42% "quite" 73.3% + 18% and "very" 0.0% + 34%) and consider the training substantial (3.3% , 7% + 50%, "very" 53.3% + 48% and "very much" 26.7%). In the survey conducted during the American School of Education (Weissberg, 2015) the participants stated they are familiar with the Program ("Not at all" 33%, "fairly" 29% and "much" 14%), have been trained in the Program "do not need more education" 15%," need more education "68% and consider training substantial (" enough "40% and "very "23%). Besides, the approach of the Program requires the training of those who will take part (C.A.S.E.L, 2003), after being implemented in the class by the teachers, having received the appropriate training (Chatzihristou, 2005). Also, a statistical difference in group rates (χ^2 , $p = 0.03 < 0.05$) was observed on this pillar in terms of acquaintance with the Program. Moreover, the comparison of the groups showed that the subjects of the experimental group were not very familiar with the Program ($2,47 \pm 0,90$, $t(78) = -2,041$, $p = 0,04$), and stated to a higher degree that the training was substantial (4.03 ± 0.76 , $t(78) = 3.91$, $p = 0.00$). In addition, female teachers were more familiar with the Program (3.18 ± 1.15 , $t(78) = -4.42$, $p = 0.00$), as well as male teachers (3.14 ± 1.10 , $t(78) = 4.11$, $p = 0.00$). The above-mentioned results seem to corroborate the importance of lifelong learning and vocational training (Brinia & Chatzichalampous, 2018).

6. Limitations of the present study and suggestions for future research

Difficulties were encountered in finding the head teachers of these schools, as many had retired due to the fact that new ones were appointed. The problem, in part, was solved (10 of the 14 head teachers took part in the survey) through many telephone communications. Also, the questionnaire included three different pillars, and, as a result, a two-stage pilot test was carried out to check its validity and reliability. Fortunately, the Easter holidays helped to ensure sufficient space between the two measurements.

Finally, the questionnaires were distributed to schools in breaks to avoid disturbing the smooth operation of the school by the researcher. That is why there was respect for both the school and the people. Even before the questionnaires were given, there was assurance that the information would be secret (Creswell, 2011) and no participant's answers would be shared.

According to the data analyzed, it is considered important to carry out the survey in a larger sample for better generalization of the results.

In addition, it would be better to look more closely at how teachers communicate with parents. As we have seen, educators expressing genuine emotions, try to manage the parents in an appropriate way, but the communication between them depends on many factors, with some of them referring to the ways they are used (Graham-Clay, 2005), the obstacles and perceptions that exist (Georgiou, 2000). It is therefore proposed to explore further the factors that make their communication difficult.

Also, teachers have stated, at fairly high rates, how satisfied they are with their profession. However, the satisfaction of the teacher's profession depends on other situations that are not mentioned in the survey. More focused research could, in the future, analyze the issues that satisfy or hinder the profession of the teacher. At high rates, women also stated that they choose the profession of the teacher more than men. It would be good future research to focus on the reasons why women prefer this profession.

7. Conclusions

This study is an attempt to investigate the teachers' emotional intelligence who have implemented the Program of Social and Emotional Intelligence in the 30th Region of Attica. It is one of the few studies of this kind that exist and reflects the teachers' views and attitudes who have implemented such programs in a particular educational district. The study shows that the teachers who participated in the research presented high scores in all three pillars of Emotional Intelligence, consider the Program beneficiary for school and deem their training and vocational training useful for the implementation of the Program.

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Appendix**Questionnaire for the Implementation of the Social and Emotional Intelligence Program****A. DEMOGRAPHICS****1. Gender**

- Male
- Female

2. Age

- 22-35
- 36-45
- 46+

3. Education

- Degree in Primary Education
- Degree at Pedagogical Academy
- Postgraduate Education
- Master's Degree

B. SERVICE INFORMATION**4. Position in School**

- Head Teacher
- Teacher

5. Education

- Less than 3 years
- 3-5 years
- 6-10
- 11-15
- 16-20
- 21-25
- 26-30

C. PILLARS

1st Pillar: *Emotional Intelligence and Vocational Training of Educators*

		1	2	3	4	5
6	I know what and how I am feeling at any given moment					
7	I can manage my emotions					
8	I am good observer of others					
9	I understand other people's emotions around me					
10	I set goals and try to achieve them					
11	I encourage myself to do my best					
12	I am characterized by composure and manage difficulties reasonably					
13	I am able, when angry, to calm down quickly using reason					
14	I properly manage students and parents					
15	I display fake emotions to students and parents					
16	I pretend to have emotions when in workplace					
17	I work hard to display the emotions I must to students and parents					
18	I show to students and parents are genuine					
19	The emotions I show to students and parents are natural and spontaneous					
20	The emotions I show to parents are natural and genuine					
21	I want to be the ideal teacher by any means necessary					
22	I am satisfied with being a teacher					
23	Being a teacher has offered me important things					
24	If I had to choose a career again, I wouldn't change anything					

2nd Pillar: *The benefits of the Social and Emotional Intelligence Program to students and the improvement of the school environment*

		I do not know	Totally Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Totally Agree
25	It creates a positive attitude towards the school					
26	It improves the working environment					
27	It improves the relationship between students and teachers					

3rd Pillar: *Teachers' Training and Vocational Training for the implementation of the Program*

28. On a scale from 1-5 (5 being very familiar and 1 not being familiar at all) how familiar are you with Social and Emotional Intelligence?

1	2	3	4	5

29. On a scale from 1-5 (5 being you have received an excellent education and 1 being no education at all) are you trained to teach social and emotional skills to students?

1	2	3	4	5

30 To what extend do you agree or disagree with the following statement?

“The training I received, was important because it substantially helped to implement the Social and Emotional Intelligence Program to my students”

Totally Disagree	Disagree a little	Agree a little	Strongly agree	Completely agree